

The National Park Management Regime in Bhutan: Historical Background and Current Problems

KLAUS SEELAND

*Swiss Federal Institute of Technology
ETH-Zentrum
CH-8092 Zürich, Switzerland*

ABSTRACT

This paper gives an account of the recent history and the international and national policy background with respect to the planning and administration of Bhutan's nine national parks, nature reserves and sanctuaries, and sheds light on their current problems. Although more than 25 per cent of Bhutanese territory has been declared protected area over the last three decades, little data is available on the local population's perception of the aims, present status and the benefits of national parks, and their future role in the regional political setting and national resource use policy. Local communities are exposed to the legal limitations of resource use. A national park regime faces the problems of integrating issues of local management with the international community's demands on biodiversity preservation and conservation, and with the objectives of a national resource use concept.

BHUTAN'S GEOGRAPHICAL AND POLITICAL SETTING

The Kingdom of Bhutan is situated on the southern slopes of the Eastern Himalayas, covering an area of 40,076 sq km (RGOB 1995b) and spanning various climatic zones, from subtropical to alpine and arctic. Southern Bhutan lies at an altitude of about 200m above sea level (a.s.l.), rising to an altitude of 7,500m a.s.l. in the north where it constitutes a part of the Great Himalayan Range. The country is renowned as one of the world's hotspots for biodiversity, where 'more than 60 per cent of the species endemic to the Eastern Himalayas are found' (RGOB et al. n.d.: 1).¹ Its environment has remained largely intact, in contrast to the major degradation which has already severely affected other areas within the Hindukush—Himalaya—Karakoram region. The country is made up of 72.5 per cent forest cover, whereas only 7.8 per cent is arable land under cultivation. Bhutan has a Five Year Plan economy and a per capita income of 478 US dollars in 1996, which thus places it among the least developed

countries in the world. This Five Year Plan economy enables those who administer the country's protected areas to develop nature conservation and sustainable protection issues as a strategic development policy.

The vast majority of the population of 640,000 (RGOB 1993a) practise Mahayana Buddhism. Buddhist values emphasise a respectful attitude towards all living beings and their protection. Despite this prevailing cultural attitude, hunting still occurs in some remote parts of the country. The Buddhist monarchy was established in its present form in 1907, when the first hereditary King Ugyen Wangchuck was elected. The monarchy is held in high esteem by the population and has, together with the monk body, an all pervading influence at every level of society. It provides Bhutan with excellent opportunities for the central administration to enact an effective nature conservation policy, which is highly appreciated by the foreign donor countries. No official research, however, has so far been undertaken concerning the perception and attitude of the rural population towards nature conservation and its impact on local life-styles. An increasing number of problems is emerging from the fact that a nature conservation policy, as a modern Western legacy, has been largely imposed on a culture consisting of predominantly self-sustained rural communities. This paper aims to provide an analysis of the salient features of the socio-cultural impact of Bhutan's national conservation policy.

THE HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF NATIONAL PARK ESTABLISHMENT IN BHUTAN

Up until 1997, approximately 26.5 per cent of Bhutanese territory has been declared protected area. The initial idea was to safeguard the wildlife of these areas, particularly the mammals. To protect species like tiger (*Panthera tigris*), leopard (*Panthera pardus*), elephant (*Elephas maximus*), gaur (*Bos gaurus*), spotted deer (*Axis axis*) and rhinoceros (*Rhinoceros unicornis*), one had to protect their respective habitat which was almost entirely forest. Thus the concept of protected areas was considered to be the necessary measure for the achievement of this goal. The first Bhutan Forest Act of 1969 (RGOB 1969) adopted the concept of Reserved Forests from India, and all forest became state forest in which many restrictions now limited the formerly free access of the users to timber and non-timber forest products. Under chapter II, 6e of the 1969 Forest Act 'poisoning water, hunting, shooting, fishing or setting traps or snares' were prohibited in Reserved Forests. Before the introduction of forest legislation, the WWF (US) helped to establish wildlife sanctuaries, parks and forest reserves. The establishment of protected areas such as wildlife sanctuaries dates back to 1966,² when King Jigme Dorji Wangchuck, the Third King of Bhutan (1952-1972), and HRH Prince Namgyel Wangchuck, the then Minister of Trade,

NATIONAL PARKS IN BHUTAN

FIGURE 1. Bhutan: national parks, nature reserves and wildlife sanctuaries. Not to scale. Source: RGOB, GIS CELL (Oct 1997).

Industries and Forest, declared that the royal family's former hunting reserves in the south were to become protected areas by Royal Government order.

In the 1960s the Forest Department consisted of a handful of individuals who resided in tents in the Thimphu Valley. Its existence was not so much for the sake of obtaining state revenue from the forest, but rather to safeguard the forest from unchecked use and exploitation due to the increasing demand of the Indian market which it was feared would go beyond the state's control. Furthermore, from the Forest Department's point of view, increasing litigation over forest related issues made it desirable to have a Forest Act in order to facilitate law suits, to contend with the criticism of the Forest Department, raised in the National Assembly, concerning their handling of forest issues, and also to make them more accountable. Substantial parts of the Thimphu Valley and the area around Wangdi Phodrang were already denuded of their forest cover at that time. In order to enact state authority, which was likely to be threatened due to the non-existence of a Civil Law Code before 1965 (Rose 1977: 209), it was felt necessary to display the overarching power of the Government by establishing forest legislation and an administration. The need for a forest policy was felt only after these two were established.

Once a Forest Department was set up, it could act as an administrative frame and a stepping-stone for the development of a nature conservation scheme. Informal and personal contacts between WWF (US) and the Royal Bhutanese Government were established in the early 1970s between some American

officials who were impressed by Bhutan's unspoilt beauty and biodiversity, and high ranking Bhutanese administrators. In fact, in those days there was no clear vision of what constituted an appropriate conservation policy for the country. In the United States, national parks were well established and appreciated as an important part of national heritage and cultural identity (Nepal and Weber 1993: 4f. *et passim*). The great North American national parks, however, were located in areas without human settlements. This was neither the case in Bhutan nor, for instance, in India or Nepal. The existence of settlements in, or close to, protected areas has become one of the major issues for conflict between the state authorities and the local population. Their customary rights to use the natural resources of their environment were reduced without any compensation by the state (Nepal and Weber 1993).

On November 1, 1974 a notification³ on the 'Creation of Wildlife Sanctuaries/Parks/Forest Reserves', issued by the Government of Bhutan, expanded the already existing and geographically demarcated eight protected areas (see Table 1), chiefly on the basis of a random assessment. There was still no nature conservation policy at that time, although the first national forest policy of 1974 attempted to harmonise the increasing number of protected areas. In the

Wildlife Sanctuaries/ Parks/Forest Reserves	Civil Jurisdiction	Forest Division	Area in sq km
1. Laya Wildlife Sanctuary	Thimphu, Ha, Paro and Gasa Dzong	Thimphu	1477
2. Gasa Wildlife Sanctuary	Gasa and Tongsa Dzong	Thimphu	2718
3. Jigme Dorji Wildlife Sanctuary	Wangdiphodrang, Tongsa, Lhuntshi and Tashigang Dzong	Thimphu, Sarbhong and Samdrup Jongkhar	3710
4. Goley Game Reserve	Sarbhong	Sarbhong	195
5. Doga National Park	Paro	Thimphu	21
6. Mochu Reserved Forests	Sarbhong	Sarbhong	278
7. Pachu Reserved Forests	Samchi	Samchi	140
8. Khaling Reserved Forests	Sarbhong	Sarbhong	233

TABLE 1. Wildlife sanctuaries, parks and forest reserves in Bhutan after 1974

Source: RGOB 1974: 3. Measurement in sq miles has been replaced by the author, because later accounts always give the size in sq km.

NATIONAL PARKS IN BHUTAN

subsequent decade the emphasis was on upgrading the protected areas and ranking them according to their assigned national and international importance.

Table 2 shows the changes made to the protected areas following a notification of February 13, 1984, when Laya, Gasa and Jigme Dorji Wildlife Sanctuaries were merged and became Jigme Dorji Wildlife Sanctuary, and Goley Game Reserve became Namgyal Wangchuck Reserve. The country's protected areas were subsequently divided into the Northern and Southern Wildlife Circles. In its 'Rules and Regulations For Preservation and Maintenance ...' this notification was based on the Forest Act of 1969, whereby under section a) His Majesty the King was entitled to grant exceptions in order to kill or capture animals, when they were 'found to be increasing to an extent endangering the preservation of any species of animals, birds *or for any other reason*' (emphasis added). The statement 'or for any other reason' shows the uncertainty of these laws; the reason did not need to be explicitly defined in the rules and regulations given in this notification. Regarding entry rights, everyone other than the native residents

Northern Wildlife Circle	Area in sq km
Jigme Dorji Wildlife Sanctuary	7813
Doga National Park	21
Total:	7834
Southern Wildlife Circle	
Pochu Wildlife Circle	140
Phibsoo Reserved Forest (formerly part of Mochu Reserve)	175
Namgyal Wangchuck Reserve (formerly Goley Reserve)	195
Manas Wildlife Sanctuary	463
Khaling Reserved Forest	233
Zoshing Reserved Forest	5
Sinchula Reserved Forest	80
Shumar Wildlife Reserve	160
Dungsum Wildlife Reserve	180
Neoli Wildlife Reserve	40
Total:	1671
Grand Total:	9505

TABLE 2. National parks, wildlife sanctuaries and reserved forests after 1984

Source: Blower 1989: 15; Notification TIF/FOR/III-8/83/7040

was subject to restrictions. Section d) of the notification states, 'Entry into the Forest blocks is prohibited except for Bhutanese civil, military and development officers on duty. Visitors are welcome but they will have to obtain the previous permission in writing of the concerned Divisional Forest Officer.'⁴ The Forestry Services Division has thus become the only administrative service that is legally permitted to undertake forest operations as per its own prescriptions laid down in the respective working plans.⁵ It is thus the immediate partner and representative of the Bhutanese Government. It deals with major aspects of local, as well as national, resource supply. The new dimension that overrides people's traditional life-style, particularly that of the farmers, is that they have to apply for the use of virtually all forest products and, after approval, to pay for what was previously available to them free of charge. These new restrictions become even more obvious within the protected areas than they already were in state forest management.

Financial gains from the revenue drawn from state forests may have begun to play a role after the first formulation of a forest policy in 1974, when the country's socio-economic development put increasing strain on the Government's financial resources. In 1955, monetarisation was introduced nationally and replaced the former revenue system involving payment in kind and labour services rendered to the state or the monastic body. However, it was only after the 1969 Forest Act that timber and other forest products were to procure revenue from royalties, fees and export, needed to cover the Government's rising financial expenditure.⁶ In light of this, it was obvious that the national parks, wildlife sanctuaries and forest reserves could only be established and maintained with foreign aid.

ACHIEVEMENTS OVER THE LAST DECADE

A process to revise the Government's Nature Conservation policy was undertaken from 1989 to 1991 together with the drafting of the Master Plan for Forestry Development (RGOB et al. 1991). However, the latter was never officially approved. Prior to this revision a Strategy for Environmental Conservation was devised for Bhutan, by WWF, in 1986 (WWF 1987), and in 1992 a WWF office was opened in Thimphu. In 1993 a Nature Conservation Division was set up under the Forest Department, that was to become the Nature Conservation Section when the Forest Department was named Forestry Services Division in 1994. Up until 1993 there was no National Conservation Strategy, although such a strategy was recommended by an FAO consultant in 1988 (Blower 1989: 25), together with suggested amendments of the National Forest Policy which was drafted in 1985, and a land-use planning programme to be implemented throughout Bhutan. On 10 September 1993 a further notification

NATIONAL PARKS IN BHUTAN

Area	Category	Area sq km	Buffer sq km	Dzongkhag
Torsa	S.N.R.	644	0	Ha/Samtse
Jigmi Dorji	N.P.	3900	300	Paro/Thimpu/Gasa/ Punakha
Black Mountain	N.P.	1300	100	Wangdue/Tongsa/ Zhemgang/Bhumtha
Thrumshing-la	N.P.	748	20	Zhemgang/Bhumtha/ Mongar
Royal Manas	N.P.	975	25	Gaylephug/Zhemgang / S.Jongkhar
Sakteng	W.S.	610	40	Trashigang
Kulong Chu	W.S.	1250	50	Lhunsi/Trashiyangtse
Phibsoo	W.S.	278	0	Gaylegphu
Khaling/Neoli	W.S.	273	0	Samdrup Jongkhar

TABLE 3. Protected areas in Bhutan after 1993

Key: S.N.R. = Strict Nature Reserve; N.P. = National Park; W.S. = Wildlife Sanctuary. Wildlife Sanctuaries and Strict Nature Reserves rank below National Parks.

Source: RGOB 1993b.

was issued by the RGOB, whereby the protected areas were revised in order 'to rationalise the biodiversity representation and protection needs'. Table 3 shows that the effective area under protection was increased to 9,978 sq km. Compared to the first demarcation of 8,772 sq km in 1974, this was an increment of 13.1 per cent. Furthermore, buffer zones were introduced to some protected areas, so that the total demarcated area amounted to 10,513 sq km in 1993, which is c. 1,000 sq km more than the area in the 1984 notification. Together with a territorial enlargement went an upgrading of the protected areas. In the process of being upgraded, some parts of Jigmi Dorji were excluded from the protected area, making the resulting National Park smaller than the original Wildlife Sanctuary. The ranking of National Park, Wildlife Sanctuary, Strict Nature Reserve and Reserved Forest reflects the order of importance given to the respective sites. Doga National Park and Mochu Reserved Forest (part of which had been incorporated into Phibsoo Reserved Forest after 1984) ceased to exist. Doga was found too small to be effective and Mochu was incorporated into Phibsoo Wildlife Sanctuary.

In the same year, the first Nature Conservation Action Plan by the Nature Conservation Section was released, pinpointing six objectives (RGOB 1993c):

1. Strengthening of the Forestry Services Division,
2. Review and revision of the national protected areas system,
3. Establishment of an information database,
4. Preparation of management and operational plans for three priority protected areas,
5. Establishment of independent management units for the protected areas identified under objective 4,
6. Development of professional manpower.

These objectives show that the major emphasis was on increasing the administrative capacity of the Nature Conservation Section. Participatory approaches or collaborative management schemes were not envisaged. An action plan consisting of between one and nine measures was formulated to ensure the achievement of each objective. Finally, a National Conservation Strategy for Bhutan was drafted in 1996, although its approval by the cabinet is still pending. However, as the conservation of nature is already centrally administered and an integral part of the Forestry Services Division, this strategy may be regarded as being largely a donor-oriented document and a guideline for the co-ordination of respective activities among the present major donors in this sector, WWF, DANIDA and SNV.⁷ Furthermore, the demand for a National Conservation Strategy seems to have been inspired, like so many other activities in matters of nature conservation and forest use, by the experiences of international agencies like WWF and IUCN in Nepal.⁸ A general worldwide approach, launched through WWF and IUCN, that follows the prescriptive policy of an international conservation standard based on the US park model, has to focus on the question of cultural appropriateness, and should, in a sense, possess the political correctness to take into account the unique natural and cultural situation of the country to which it is applied. A one-world approach to conservation, irrespective of whether it is suitable for the socio-cultural conditions of small or developing countries, could be fatal. As a Third World country's economy is not, and may never be, in a position to manage its protected areas according to Western standards, in a self-sustained way, it may thus become a constant recipient of foreign financial aid. The only opportunity for some independence in these matters would be the marketing of the national park areas in the tourism sector. However, considering the present restrictive tourism policy of the RGOB, the management of protected areas cannot be made sustainable by income generated from national park tourism. Furthermore, the notion of large-scale park tourism for Bhutan would contradict the objective of sparing protected areas from human interference wherever possible. As the National Conservation Action Plan

NATIONAL PARKS IN BHUTAN

clearly states, park management focuses on institution building, management issues, applied research, and human resources development.

The last decade of Bhutan's national policies concerning conservation and the national parks, is clearly oriented towards the establishment of a professional management capacity with an adequately developed administrative structure and a sufficient number of well trained staff. For example, the two existing management plans for the Royal Manas National Park, 1995-2000 (RGOB and WWF 1995) and the Jigme Dorji National Park, 1996/97-2000/01 (RGOB and WWF 1997) state that tourism within the parks will be allowed, but is 'secondary in priority to nature conservation and the need to protect the ecosystem ...' (RGOB and WWF 1995: 46, 1997: 43). The same policy is followed in the draft versions of the management plans for the Black Mountain National Park⁹ and Bomdiling Wildlife Sanctuary (to be established soon).¹⁰ For the Jigme Dorji National Park, however, a feasibility study for the development of an eco-tourism scheme as part of an integrated management project, is drafted under the UNDP Global Environmental Facility Programme and the Ministry of Agriculture.

CURRENT STATE AND PROBLEMS OF THE NATIONAL PARK MANAGEMENT REGIME

In 1997 there are ten foreign donor countries assisting Bhutan in environmental and nature conservation issues. Furthermore, there are two national organisations that are also active in this sector. One is the Bhutan Trust Fund for Environmental Conservation (BTF), which was signed in 1991 and became operational in 1992. The BTF generally funds conservation programmes where no other foreign donor assistance is either available or desirable. In 1997 the Global Environmental Facility (UNDP), WWF (US), the Netherlands, Norway, Denmark, Finland and Switzerland contribute to the fund's financial assets of 25 million US dollars, which is managed by a board of directors and supervised by the World Bank. An annual income of about 11 per cent from the capital's interest flows into nature conservation. Nature Conservation policy in Bhutan has thus become a meeting point of international initiatives to invest in a politically rewarding sphere of global interest.

The second organisation is the Royal Society for the Protection of Nature (RSPN), a non-governmental organisation funded predominantly by WWF, the MacArthur Foundation, which is engaged in nature protection, and other internationally operating NGOs. It is primarily concerned with environmental education and awareness building programmes. Some additional money is procured from conducting studies or programmes on behalf of the Government administration. In addition to these efforts, a wide range of activities focusing on

environment and biodiversity protection are undertaken by the Nature Conservation Section under the Forest Services Division within the regular forest management plans, as all general guidelines in the forestry sector focus on measures which are in accordance with the Government's overall environmental policy.

The current situation of Bhutan's national park regime is characterised by man-made problems which are sometimes aggravated by the precarious bio-physical conditions in the country. Table 4 gives a clear overview of the situation in Bhutan's climatic zones, where human activities have a negative impact on the respective natural surroundings. With an annual population growth of 3.1 per cent (1993), it is likely that Bhutan's population will have doubled by 2018. It is assumed that the consumption pattern, particularly of the population dwelling in the country's larger towns, will continue to rise, and that the state will have to face the population's increasing demands and expectations for services and the provision of infrastructure such as roads, energy supply, water, sanitation and communication. Added to this is the vast Indian market with its growing demand for timber and a whole variety of other renewable natural resources such as hydro-power, fruit and medicinal herbs.

Table 4 indicates that the threats to Bhutan's resource base have already gained momentum. Unfortunately, at present there is insufficient socio-economic data for assessments concerning the extent of resource use by the different sections of society, varying local supply and demand, cash flow, and market

Alpine zone	Overgrazing <i>Alpine pasture fires</i> <i>Illegal collection of medicinal plants by intruders from China</i> Poisoning of predators
Temperate zone	Shifting cultivation Forest fires Clearing of forests for orchards <i>Logging and unregulated use of timber and NTFP</i>
Subtropical zone	Poaching Mining Encroachment <i>Guerilla war activities</i>

TABLE 4. Threats to biodiversity in Bhutan

Source: adapted from S. Wangchuck 1995 and supplemented or altered slightly by the author. Changes are shown in italics.

NATIONAL PARKS IN BHUTAN

commodities and services. All of these have considerable influence on the respective regional and local economies within the country and an impact on the national park and protected area regime in the different regions. Socio-economic and socio-cultural assessments on a nationwide database would therefore be a prerequisite for a sound national renewable resource management regime in general, and in particular for the protected areas in the more densely populated middle montane and subtropical lowland zone bordering India.¹¹ Furthermore, it seems appropriate for a country like Bhutan, where Buddhism plays such an important role in all spheres of social life, to have empirical data on the location, size and religious importance of sacred sites or groves, and their socio-economic implications with respect to the restrictions bestowed on them according to the perceptions of the local people. For the local population living inside protected areas it is hard to understand why the land has been declared protected area at all, and who benefits from the restrictions imposed on land and resource use. Bhutan is a society in which the administration is perceived as a strong and hierarchical power by the rural peasants, who make up approximately 90 per cent of Bhutan's population. The enactment of the Forestry Services Division's power has expanded from the Forest Act 1969 to the Forest and Nature Conservation Act 1995 (RGOB 1995a) not only in terms of an increased size of protected territory, but it has also expanded its responsibilities and function. The tightening legal control over landuse and renewable natural resources through the administration has thus become an additional source of legitimacy or, one should say, state dominance. The state has become the mediator of the country's natural wealth and beauty, using international aid for conservation purposes as a form of capacity-strengthening for its administration. The 'administered environment' has to some extent led to its alienation from a Buddhist worldview in which every living being is part of nature and thereby has free access to it. The present King of Bhutan, H. M. Jigme Singye Wangchuck, for instance, substantially reduced the number of species to be protected that were listed in the draft of the Forest and Nature Conservation Act 1995, in order to grant as many user rights to his subjects as possible. The King, being an enlightened monarch, seems to realise the increasing contradiction between free access to natural resources, particularly for the survival of the rural poor, and international eagerness to promote nature protection.

The National Park Management is a section under the Forestry Services Division, and thus, a body of the Central Government. Its central aim is the enactment, protection and control of the country's nature conservation policy, and its duties include patrolling, habitat management, and habitat and species monitoring. One of its major responsibilities is the planning, preparation and implementation of conservation and management plans for the national parks and other protected areas. Other tasks involve conducting environmental education for school children and the general public, and awareness programmes aimed predominantly at the local population. The major issues to be tackled by

the Nature Conservation Section include crop damage by the increasing wildlife inside and outside protected areas, and wildlife attacking domestic animals and villagers. There is an obvious need for a sustainable wildlife regulation and compensation scheme, but the Forest and Nature Conservation Act 1995 has made no provisions to solve this problem. Another important task is to harmonise conservation objectives and local people's daily requirements of timber and non-timber forest products. The conflicts over crop damage due to an increasing number of wildlife and resource use restrictions, that resulted in the years after certain areas were declared protected, led to a management policy based on close cooperation with the people inhabiting the protected areas and the local block and district authorities, but not to any formal institutional participation.

Activities threatening Bhutan's natural wealth are perpetrated by different sections of Bhutanese society who engage in illegal tree felling and poaching of endangered species like tiger (*Panthera tigris*) and musk deer (*Moschus chrysogaster*). Intruders, including the Tibetan gangs who cross the border to collect highly valuable mushrooms and medicinal herbs such as *Yartsaguen-boop* (*Cordiceps sinensis*) and *Tsekha* (*Fritillaria delavayi*), have become a nuisance to the Northern Wildlife Circle.¹² If caught by the Bhutanese national park authorities, they are regularly sent back without being brought to trial or fined, in order to avoid political arguments with China. Similarly, political activists and militant Guerilla fighters of the Bodo Security Force and the United Liberation Front of Assam (ULFA) are intruding into the southern national parks, particularly into the eastern parts of Royal Manas National Park, in order to escape prosecution by the Indian Army. The Bodos, an Assamese tribe, whose activists claim to fight against the exploitation of Assam by non-Assamese Indian industrialists and big business traders, have started to challenge the Bhutanese authorities by raiding outposts of the Forest Services Division and by killing four policemen. In autumn 1997, following an increase in such incidents, the Indian Army proceeded to close all roads of minor importance between Assam and Bhutan, and plans to lay mines there. The three major routes into Bhutan are meticulously controlled by the Indian Army and Intelligence. The Bodos are held responsible for the illegal felling of high value timber species and the poaching of rare and lucrative animal species which are sold to purchase arms and medical supplies. Professional poachers and middlemen who sell products from endangered species to Kathmandu, Singapore and Beijing, make huge profits from this illegal trade. The culprits often go undetected because the Bhutanese Government is not in a position to intervene due to its lack of well trained policemen or soldiers who are able to match these well armed professionals.

A problem which has not been officially recorded but appears to be quite frequent and likely to worsen, concerns compensation for local villagers, whose lives and property are threatened by attacks from wildlife. At present, compensation payments are neither discussed nor has any policy decision been taken to draft a scheme that will ease the burden on inhabitants of the parks and protected

NATIONAL PARKS IN BHUTAN

areas. Politically, it is a particularly sensitive matter for the Bhutanese Government, which fears it could perhaps trigger, among other things, an unaccountable wave of financial demands and possible litigation. The RGOB is not equipped with enough trained personnel to be able to cope with this problem. Although this will become an unavoidable issue in the future, as yet there is merely an unofficial awareness that this will prove a major obstacle to wildlife and biodiversity conservation and to developing a good relationship with the village communities concerned.

Another problem that will emerge in the future is that of population growth and, particularly in the Northern Wildlife Circle, the rapidly increasing number of livestock. In Jigme Dorji National Park overgrazing has already occurred, and the animals belonging to livestock rearing nomads compete with wildlife over the dwindling fodder resources. To deal with the problem an Enclave and Buffer Zone Management Policy, a Multiple-use Zone Policy and a Seasonal Grazing Zone Policy have been included in the Management Plan. Furthermore, there is a Medicinal Incense Plant Harvesting Policy, a Tourism Policy, an Education Policy and a Fire Policy (RGOB and WWF 1997: 41-44). These particular policies are an extension of the policies to be found in the Royal Manas National Park Management Plan that was issued in 1995 (see RGOB and WWF 1995: 49-58), including emerging problem issues in the Northern Wildlife Circle. However, it will remain an open question as to whether the compartmentalisation of policy approaches can provide the Park Management staff with the capacity to solve these problems by giving them the attention they require. Personnel may well become overburdened by the sheer number and range of management objectives and time consuming tasks (such as patrolling) which, combined with their dependence on a good relationship with the local communities, makes the enactment of all these policies somewhat doubtful.

CONCLUSION

The national park management regime in Bhutan, in its present form and with its present responsibilities, is basically a result of two cultures: the international conservationist perspective and a national nature protection policy that tries to unite the former with Buddhist values. It is an institution which was established predominantly with the help of foreign inspiration and financial assistance, and it has imposed Western conservation values on a strong Buddhist value system. The Nature Conservation Section under the Forestry Services Division, which itself is a subunit of the Ministry of Agriculture, takes the salient features of the national forest policy and the objectives of the Renewable Natural Resources Sector policy into account, in order to meet the international standards of nature conservation, and to safeguard Bhutan's prominent position in the world in terms of its rich biodiversity and share of rare and endemic flora and fauna. The major

challenges to be faced are politically or economically motivated trans-border disturbances from neighbouring intruders, the increase of livestock which is threatening the fodder base of wildlife, and damage to crops and injury to domestic livestock and humans residing in and around the protected areas due to an increase in wildlife. Furthermore, there is an increase in poaching and forest offences sanctioned under the Forest and Nature Conservation Act 1995 (Wangchuck 1997).¹³ The wide ranging National Conservation Strategy which attempts to integrate as many environmental and developmental goals as possible at a time, with rather limited financial resources and trained personnel, has itself become a stumbling block in the successful implementation of nature conservation. Whether the fact that the section is an administrative unit under the Forestry Services Division helps or hinders its intended function, which is to act in a balanced way on behalf of nature conservation, local communities, national forestry assets and international expectations, remains to be seen. Tourism or, one should say, eco-tourism, which is presently a negligible factor in the country's economy, could be of increasing importance in terms of the income generated from protected areas in the future. The major challenge for the Government, however, will be the establishment of a good relationship with the rural population that may pave the way for a participatory approach to managing Bhutan's natural wealth, in the form of its national parks, together with the local inhabitants. The satisfaction of local subsistence needs as well as the global demands of nature conservation will ultimately decide upon the continuation of a policy that has produced so many encouraging achievements over the last 30 years. Only if it turns out to be socially and culturally sustainable at the national level in the long term, may it be called an achievement for nature and culture, for endangered species and equally endangered life-styles.

NOTES

¹ See RGOB 1996, Part III, Chapter 9 (Environment and Development).

² This order was issued on 11 July 1966 by Kheden Tamgi Jagar, Secretary General of the RGOB and later Home Minister.

³ Approval no. TIF-11/74 by His Majesty's Government of Bhutan (RGOB 1974).

⁴ All sanctuaries, parks and forest reserves are referred to as 'forest block'.

⁵ Section e): Under no circumstances felling of trees or cutting of shrubs and bushes shall be permitted except those provided by prescriptions of working plan and executed by the Forest Department.

⁶ In 1997 timber export, predominantly to India, is the second most important contribution to the GNP.

⁷ DANIDA is the Danish International Development Agency and SNV is the Netherlands Development Organisation.

⁸ IUCN prepared a National Conservation Strategy for Nepal in the mid 1980s (HMGN and IUCN 1988) after a World Conservation Strategy had been proclaimed by IUCN,

NATIONAL PARKS IN BHUTAN

UNEP and WWF in 1980 (IUCN 1980).

⁹This project will be financially assisted by the Sustainable Development Agreement (SDA) with c. 3.5 million US dollars.

¹⁰An agreement has been signed for financial assistance by DANIDA worth 2 million US dollars over a period of five years.

¹¹Some socio-economic studies focusing on forest management and conservation have already been undertaken over the last decade such as Janze 1985, Upadhyay 1988 and D.Wangchuck 1995. However, these studies are either project- or problem-oriented. No systematic and longitudinal studies are available covering these aspects at a nationwide level.

¹²According to the offence records of the Nature Conservation Section, Forestry Services Division, Ministry of Agriculture, RGOB, the number of detected cases amounted to ten in the period from June to September 1997. In total 76 people, who had illegally collected 417 pieces of *Cordiceps sinensis* and 14 kg of *Fritillaria delavayi*, were sent back to Chinese territory by the Bhutanese Park authorities according to the Progress Report 1/ 6 - 30/9/1997 of the Lingtshi Warden, Jigme Dorji National Park (File No. LWP 1-7, 97-2, dated 15/10/97).

¹³S. Wangchuck (1997, Ch.3.6.2) gives a detailed review of all reported cases from 1991-1996 showing that out of a total number of 256 cases which were reported during this period, poaching was the most common offence, making up 33 per cent of the detected cases. Illegal felling (30 per cent) was second, followed by illegal fishing and illegal appropriation of forest products (14 per cent each). Sixty per cent of the offences occurred in rural areas and 63 per cent were committed by farmers. Approximately 30 per cent of the offences happened within parks and protected areas amounting to c. 50 per cent of the fines (personal communication S. Wangchuck, November 1997).

REFERENCES

- Blower, J. H. 1989. *Nature Conservation in Northern and Central Bhutan*. FAO, FO: BHU/85/016, Field Document No.1. Rome.
- HMGN and IUCN (International Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources) (eds) 1988. *Building on Success. The National Conservation Strategy for Nepal*. His Majesty's Government of Nepal. Kathmandu.
- IUCN 1980. *World Conservation Strategy. Living Resource Conservation for Sustainable Development*. IUCN, United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) and World Wildlife Fund (WWF). Gland, Switzerland.
- Janze, H.-G. 1985. *Report on the Socio-economic Baseline Survey for Establishing Social Forestry Models in Two Selected Blocks around Phumtsholing*. Field Document No. 3, Forest Management and Conservation Project, BHU/85/016, Department of Forests, RGOB and FAO. Thimphu.
- Nepal, S. K. and Weber, K. E. 1993. *Struggle for Existence. Park—People Conflict in the Royal Chitwan National Park, Nepal*. Asian Institute of Technology, Division of Human Settlements Development. Bangkok.
- Rose, Leo E. 1977. *The Politics of Bhutan*. Cornell University Press. Ithaca.
- RGOB 1969. *The Bhutan Forest Act*. RGOB Ministry of Trade, Industries and Forests. Thimphu.

- RGOB 1974. *Creation of Wild Life Sanctuaries/Parks/Forest Reserves*. Notification No. TIF—11/74 (1.11.74). RGOB Ministry of Agriculture and Forests, Department of Forests. Thimphu.
- RGOB 1993a. *Statistical Yearbook of Bhutan*. RGOB Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization. Thimphu.
- RGOB 1993b. *Notification No. AFD/FO/1C-5/93/1464*, dated 10/9/1993. RGOB Ministry of Agriculture. Thimphu.
- RGOB 1993c. *Nature Conservation Action Plan*. RGOB Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry Services Division, Nature Conservation Section. Thimphu.
- RGOB 1995a. *Forest and Nature Conservation Act 1995*. Thimphu.
- RGOB 1995b. Ministry of Agriculture, Landuse Statistics Section. Database. Thimphu.
- RGOB 1996. *Eighth Five Year Plan (1997-2002)*, Vol. I Main Document. RGOB Ministry of Planning. Thimphu.
- RGOB, DANIDA, ADB 1991. *Master Plan For Forestry Development*, prepared by COWI consult, JAAKKO POEYRY. Thimphu.
- RGOB and WWF 1995. *Royal Manas National Park, Bhutan: Conservation Management Plan, 1995-2000*. RGOB Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry Services Division, Nature Conservation Section. Thimphu.
- RGOB and WWF 1997. *Jigme Dorji National Park. Conservation Management Plan, 1996-97 to 2000-01*. RGOB Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry Services Division, Nature Conservation Section. Thimphu.
- RGOB, United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and WWF n.d. *Prospectus. Trust Fund for Environmental Conservation in Bhutan*. Thimphu.
- Upadhyay, K. P. 1988. *Shifting Cultivation in Bhutan: present situation and alternatives*. FAO/TCP/BHU/6653, Field Document No.1. Rome.
- Wangchuck, D. 1995. *Factors that Affect Local Participation in Community Forestry: A Case Study of Success/Failure of Community Woodlots in Punakha Dzongkhag, Bhutan*. Msc Thesis, ITC Netherlands.
- Wangchuck, S. 1995. *Biodiversity Conservation in Bhutan*. Nature Conservation Section, Forestry Services Division, Ministry of Agriculture. Thimphu.
- Wangchuck, S. 1997. *Local Perceptions and Indigenous Institutions as Forms of Social Performance for Sustainable Forest Management in Bhutan*. Doctoral Thesis, ETH Zurich, No.12217 (unpublished). Zurich.
- WWF 1987. *Bhutan. Strategy for Environmental Conservation*. World Wildlife Fund. Washington D.C.